

Characterization of an Advanced Airborne Radiation Detector System for the ARES Project

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Abstract—The Airborne Radiological Enhanced-sensor System (ARES) Advanced Technology Demonstration (ATD) has the goal of improving capabilities to detect, localize, track, and identify illicit radiological and/or nuclear material in airborne search scenarios. The Department of Homeland Security divided the project into two separate research and development tasks that are being supported; hardware development and advanced algorithms. The hardware task developed four synchronized arrays of 26 CsI(Na) detectors, a suite of contextual sensors, and a 'prior' database that provides additional context on search areas. The algorithm teams are developing algorithms that leverage the contextual sensors and the modernized detector system. Their efforts are focused in three areas: improving detection algorithms for CsI(Na) detectors; improving awareness of background fluctuations due to variability in the composition and topography of terrain; and leveraging the imaging capabilities of the detector and the contextual sensors to improve the ability to localize and track static and moving gamma-ray sources. This paper highlights the efforts of the team working in support of the Domestic Nuclear Detection Office (DNDO) to characterize the R&D products and to assess and highlight technological advances and the potential for further performance improvements that could result from the ARES ATD.

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental radioactivity measurements have been conducted from airborne platforms for many decades. They have been used to study dispersion of radioactive materials from nuclear weapons tests and nuclear accidents, as well as for broad surveys of mineral formations and of soil moisture[1]-[3]. The broad areas over which such measurements can be made is an attractive component for conducting such surveys from airborne platforms has also been identified as a potential strength for search missions[4]. However, the most commonly deployed system[5] has not been designed for search missions.

The Airborne Radiological Enhanced-sensor System (ARES) project was initiated by the Domestic Nuclear Detection Office (DNDO) as an Advanced Technology Demonstration (ATD) with the goal of improving capabilities to detect, localize, track, and identify illicit radiological and/or nuclear (R/N) material in airborne search missions. In the initial phase of the project, LBNL and RSL scientists performed modeling studies to highlight research and development avenues that would most likely produce capability improvements[6][7]. Although large arrays of detectors with excellent energy resolution, such as arrays of high purity germanium[8] were identified as amongst the most powerful technological capabilities, the goal of developing technologies that could be widely fielded led the team to identify sensor fusion techniques, object tracking, contextual

Fig. 1. Photograph of the ARES detector system.

awareness, imaging capabilities, and algorithm advances as means to potentially improve scintillator-based detection system capabilities that would produce more economically viable systems.

II. ARES R&D TOPICS

DNDO organized the current phase of the ARES ATD as a two-topic R&D effort with a characterization effort led by the original scoping team (LBNL and RSL). Topic 1 R&D focused on sensor package development and producing additional contextual awareness software. This effort was completed by an industry supplier and produced 92 time-synchronized CsI(Na) detectors with dual photomultiplier readouts arranged in an active mask configuration to improve angular resolution in the roll-dimension of the helicopter. Each detector is 1"x1"x16" and has approximately 1" longitudinal position resolution and 6-7% FWHM energy resolution at 662 keV. The A photo of the detector array, mounted on the test helicopter, with the endcap removed is provided as Fig. 1. After taking possession of the detector system, the characterization team characterized and implemented an improved γ -ray event reconstruction method, which is summarized in ref. [9]. Contextual sensors include a high-definition video camera array enabling target tracking and visual-based segmentation, a GPS/INU and a radar altimeter for positioning and stance, and a weather sensor. Example images obtained by the down-looking unit in the camera array

Fig. 2. Video imagery collected by ARES system. Tracking software provides unique identification numbers and bounding boxes of identified moving vehicles (example on left-hand side). Characterization will determine whether, and in what, scenarios tracking provides improved detection and localization capabilities.

are provided in Fig. 2. The software includes a target tracking capability that highlights moving vehicles within each video frame and a topographic database containing surfaces and classes of materials associated with segmented surface *tiles*. An example of the tracking capability is shown on the left-hand side of Fig.2

The second R&D topic relates to developing algorithms that leverage the contextual information and the modernized radiation detector system. There are two teams spanning national laboratories and industry that are being funded to contribute to this R&D topic. The algorithm teams' efforts are focused in three areas: improving detection algorithms for CsI(Na) detectors; improving awareness of background fluctuations due to variability in the composition and topography of terrain; and leveraging the imaging capabilities of the detector and the contextual sensors to improve the ability to localize gamma-ray sources. The detection algorithm work primarily involves incorporating the unique characteristics of the CsI(Na) array into existing state-of-the-art detection capabilities and training the decision-making aspects of the algorithms on pertinent datasets. The detection algorithms may also incorporate data fusion via alarm threshold adjustments or feedback from other software components. Localization algorithms being developed use Bayesian or maximum likelihood approaches to identify locations of static or moving sources within a field of view, while taking into account the time-varying position and stance of the detector system and the active mask encoding. Improving and leveraging background awareness is the most nebulous portion of the R&D effort. Much of the effort has been to help provide background estimators for detection and localization algorithms, and to provide segmentation to maximum likelihood algorithms. Although performance improvements have already been shown by Topic 2 vendors, the primary characterization of algorithm performance is ongoing.

III. CHARACTERIZATION OUTLOOK

The goal of the characterization is to quantify how well the hardware system and data analysis software combine to detect and localize R/N sources in a variety of environments and configurations and to determine which aspects of the

Fig. 3. Fractional R_i value for organic material calculated for arbitrary positions 300' above a region in the Las Vegas metropolitan area overlaid upon satellite imagery. The color scale is linear, ranging from 0 (dark blue) to 1 (dark red).

system provide the most value or have the most potential. As such, data collection missions have been performed in urban, semi-urban, suburban, rural, and maritime environments in various climates and with and without radioactive test sources. The aerial measurements with ground-based test sources are primarily to inform algorithm development and to benchmark source injection methods, which are planned to provide the portion of the source data used in the characterization effort. See ref. [10] for further details.

Variations in environmental radiation have been observed to severely affect the performance of radiation detection systems. With the material and topographic databases, the impact of these effects can be studied to a level of detail that is uncommon. For example, the instantaneous effective contribution from each identified material class, i , has to the the detector system's response, $R_i(t)$, can be quantified, as

$$R_i(t) = \sum_j A_{ij} \epsilon(\Omega_{r_j}) \exp(-\mu|r_j|)/|r_j|^2 \quad (1)$$

where A_{ij} is the area of the j 'th discretized terrain tile of material i visible to the detector at time t , $\epsilon(\Omega_{r_j})$ is the effective detection sensitivity of the detector from the direction, r_j , and $\exp(-\mu|r_j|)$ accounts for air attenuation. These values can be determined a posteriori to quantify the exact expected contributions from each segment and to quantify the environmental variability of a particular measurement. They have also been used to support data collection planning by identifying the general variability of potential test regions. For example, pre-calculated relative contributions from organic materials to arbitrary positions at 300 ft above ground is shown for a portion of the Las Vegas metropolitan area in Fig. 3. This particular portion of Las Vegas has some regions of very high organic concentration (for Las Vegas) that abut areas of more typical concentrations (very low).

Quantifying performance with respect different measurement scenarios including different levels of background radioactivity, track density, man-made structures, and variabil-

ity due to terrain, material, and radiological variability; and comparing system performance when confronted with differing levels of training and in various environments will help highlight operational capabilities and needs, and the maturity and flexibility of the algorithms and the system as a whole. Artificially noising (and improving where possible) the data provided to algorithms will additionally highlight how important the quality of various datastreams are for overall performance. This talk describes these and other considerations as well as the overall data collection campaign, which was completed in September, 2015.

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